

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE POLYMERIZATION OF 1-CHLORO-3-PIPERIDINE-2-PROPANOL WITH METHACRYLIC ACID

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One of the most problematic branches of radical polymerization is emulsion polymerization, the creation of a general theory of which encounters fundamental difficulties. This is due to the multiphase nature of the emulsion system, the variety of parameters that determine the kinetics and mechanism of the process and depend not only on the reactivity of the reagents, but also on the nature of their distribution over phases, the topochemistry of the reaction, and the method and mechanism of nucleation and stabilization of particles. Classical ideas about this reaction often turn out to be insufficient, especially for describing the polymerization processes of monomers with relatively high water solubility. The patterns of copolymerization of acrylic acid and (meth)acrylic esters of various structures in organic solvents and in the absence of solvents are well studied [1]. Copolymers of (meth)acrylic esters and acrylic acid (AA) are used in various industries as thickeners, emulsifiers, and stabilizers of the physicochemical properties of systems [2].

The most promising of the monomers containing the amino group of the acrylic and methacrylic series is N,N-dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate (DMAEM), on the basis of which the polymers have thermo- and pH-sensitive properties. Its copolymers are used in the production of flocculants, in the targeted administration of drugs and in the control of the rate of their separation from the carrier in the human body [3], in biotechnology and other fields of medicine. Currently, industrial polymeric materials are mainly obtained by radical polymerization. The main advantages of this method are the simplicity of its implementation, high speed, and a large number of monomers with radical polymerization. One of the genes that plays an important role in this series of monomers is monomers that contain nitrogen-fixing heterocyclic substituents [4-5]. Many high-molecular compounds, including polymers containing caprolactam, pyrrolidone, morpholin, pyridine, piperidine fragments, are found in various areas of the economy due to their solubility, complex formation and low toxicity in water and organic solvents.

In subsequent processes, a gravimetric method was used to study the kinetics of spontaneous polymerization reactions of 1-chloro-3-piperidine-2-propyl methacrylate. The influence of the monomer concentration on the polymerization reaction was determined (Table 2).

TABLE 2.

Influence of the nature of the solvent (H₂O), temperature and time on the process of CLPPMA polymerization. [M]=0.1mol/l

Substance name	Temperature, °C	Polymerization time, min.	Product yield,%
1-chloro-3-piperidine-2-propyl methacrylate	20	300	80
	30	250	86
	40	200	94
	50	180	96

According to the results obtained, the yield of the obtained product increased with increasing temperature and polymerization time [11]. In the following process, the polymerization reaction rate of 1-chloro-3-piperidine-2-propyl methacrylate and the viscosity of the resulting polymers were determined (Table 3).

TABLE 3.

Effect of monomer concentration on polymerization reaction rate and viscosity of CLPPMA polymer; solvent - water; T= 50 °C

[M], mol/l	V·10 ⁻⁴ , mol/l	[η], dl/g
0,1	2,74	0,35
0,3	3.12	0,38

0,5	5,8	0,45
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. The thermal stability of polymers was studied by differential thermal and thermogravimetric methods (Fig. 3).

FIGURE. 3. Thermogram of PCLPPMA polymer at 75°C.

Differential modes of heating and spheroid samples were carried out in the atmosphere at temperatures up to 200 - 600°C. From here, the endothermic and exothermic points of the samples were confirmed. As can be seen from Figure 3, the DTA curve of the polymer based on PCLPPMA is characterized by an endothermic maximum at 234°C and the presence of one glass transition region (267°C).

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